

IRRIGATION INSTRUMENT MODERNIZATION REFORM IN UZBEKISTAN

Shomurotov Sharofiddin Shukurjon o'gli

Teacher of Kokand State Pedagogical Institute

E-mail: sh.shomurotov7707@gmail.com

Abstract: The article analyzes the implementation of reforms in the water management system in Uzbekistan during the years of independence, special attention is paid to the rational and economical use of water resources in the irrigation system of the republic, and the modernization processes in the field are gradually improving from year to year with the help of sources. . In this regard, in order to develop the system and guarantee it legally, a number of decisions and laws were developed and the issues of their implementation were revealed.

Key words: water management, water resources, reclamation and irrigation, irrigation technologies, reservoir, canal and collectors, reform.

Agricultural production in the republic is directly related to water use. 55 billion per year on average for irrigation of cultivated fields in the republic. m³ of water is required, and this amount of water is almost half of the total water resources consumed in Central Asian countries. At the moment, more than 80% of the water used in the agriculture of the republic flows from the territories of neighboring countries, which limits the possibility of establishing the stability of the water regime.

Therefore, the economic importance of economical use of water is very high, and it is necessary to maintain the condition of irrigation and reclamation networks for use. In this regard, I.A. Karimov's "...paying special attention to the issues of ensuring the appropriate technical condition of operating irrigation and melioration facilities, strengthening

the material and technical base of specialized water management, construction and operation organizations, equipping them with modern equipment..." The tasks set in this regard will serve as a direction in the reform of the water management system. At the same time, a number of measures have been taken to improve the water use system in recent years. In particular, according to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 24, 2003 No. PF-3226 "On the most important directions of deepening economic reforms in agriculture", the development of farms was set as a priority task and reforms in this regard for the purpose of further deepening, on the basis of the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 290 of June 28, 2003, important changes took place in water management, from the principle of administrative-territorial management of water resources to the principle of basin management.

As a result of priority development of farms, the water use system has become more complicated. In particular, previously, agricultural land was at the disposal of cooperative farms, and they were also responsible for providing water to the area. The fact that there are many farms that use internal canals, hydrotechnical structures and melioration techniques, properties in one farm area, as well as many farms in the area are also water consumers by growing agricultural products. its emergence naturally removes the need for the activity of the entity that regulates the relations of water use at the lower level. This issue is regulated by Water Consumer Unions (SIU) in most developed countries. It is known that the agricultural sector plays an important role in the sustainable development of our country's economy.

That is why the government of the republic pays enough attention to the development of this industry. After all, the sustainable development of the agricultural sector is directly related to the effective operation of the water management system. In particular, the investments directed to the

modernization of the industry are aimed at ensuring the future development of this industry and serving the well-being of the country's population as a leading industry. In this regard, taking into account the important role and importance of the water management system in the economy of our country, which is the core of the agro-industrial complex, technical and technological renewal of the network and radical modernization of the sector are urgent at the next stage of the ongoing organizational-structural and financial-economic reforms. became one of the issues. After all, the analyzes of the current technical condition of water management objects "... 23.5 percent of inter-farm and main canals, 17.4 percent of intra-farm irrigation networks require repair, there are 42 water replacement of 18 hydroelectric networks and modernization of hydromechanical equipment, reconstruction of 5, repair and reconstruction of 80 percent of large pumping stations, 50 percent of medium stations, and 30 percent of small stations, cleaning of nearly 19,000 km of open drains in domestic farms requires that more than 50 percent of closed drains do not work.

To eliminate the mentioned situation, to ensure the effective operation of the water management system, a large amount of financial resources will be directed. Attracting internal and external investments for this will create an opportunity to solve the situation. That is why, as First President I.A. Karimov said, "All of us need to understand a simple fact - without investments, there will be no modernization and renewal."

The implemented reforms made it possible to eliminate redundant links between the source of water and the direct consumers of water, to develop and implement the planning and distribution of water use and management on a scientific basis, and to control the targeted use of budget funds. At the same time, based on the requirements of the economic reforms implemented in the agriculture of our republic, a number of new systems have been introduced at the lowest level of water use. One of such systems is the organization of

Water Consumer Unions (SUU). SIUs are based on the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 8 of January 5, 2003 "On measures to transform agricultural enterprises into farms" and within the requirements of Article 72 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan was established as a non-profit, non-governmental organization, and mainly finances its activities from the fees of water consumers. "Procedure for regulation of mutual water management relations in the territory of reorganized agricultural enterprises" approved by the mentioned decision No. 8 legally regulated the voluntary association for collective use. SIUs enable the development of organizational and economic relations in the water management subsystem and serve the tasks of operating the irrigation and melioration networks owned by the former joint-stock farms, supplying the required water to the established farms in a timely manner. SIUs are primarily non-profit and non-governmental organizations formed and managed by water users who depend on specific irrigation-reclamation systems. That is, the Association of Water Consumers is an association of farms, farmers and other water consumers that carry out economic activities related to taking a certain amount of water, its effective use and discharge. Water consumers in agriculture are farmers and peasant farms and other water consumers who carry out economic and other activities related to receiving a limited amount of water, using it and internal water management objects. The purpose of establishing SIUs is to combine the technical and financial capabilities of consumers for efficient use of water in the union territory by establishing fair water distribution and efficient use of irrigation and improvement networks at the lowest level of water use in agriculture. Based on the analysis, it is necessary to establish the activities of SIUs aimed at improving the water distribution system at the lower level and the role of direct economic reforms in deepening and solving the following problems of the development of water use relations of farms directly related.

Irrigation and reclamation systems, in particular water reservoirs, hydrotechnical facilities, irrigation facilities, canals and pumping stations, which are the object of investment activity in the water industry, ensure the activities of water management organizations. Therefore, their non-stop and non-emergency storage and continuous supply, as well as the provision of agricultural production with irrigation water based on the construction of new irrigation systems, depends on special conditions and specific characteristics of the system. is liq. Also, the technical condition of constantly moving water resources and irrigation networks, as well as the need to regularly monitor the sources of water resources formation and change, once again proves the consideration of system features.

The sources of increasing investment activity in the system are the funds allocated directly from the state budget funds, loans received from foreign financial organizations on the basis of state mediation and guarantees, and funds directly provided by foreign countries in the form of mutual economic assistance. and at the expense of technical means, funds transferred by foreign companies and organizations on the basis of contracts, and own funds of agricultural enterprises. In general, when increasing investment activity in the water industry, the following features need to be taken into account: – value is created only in the subsystem of the water industry system, the rest of the systems operate as links that serve it; – an integration process between non-governmental and non-profit organizations and farms and organizations operating with other types of ownership is created; – the development of the water management system is interested in increasing the income of water consumers. Because this situation is a source of development of SIUs for keeping irrigation systems in working order and payments for water resources supplied to water consumers under the contract.

The needs for the restoration of water infrastructure can be summarized as follows:

- 32.1 percent (22.3 thousand kilometers) of the total length of inter-farm and highway canals require reconstruction, and 23.5 percent require repair;
- more than 42.1 percent (149.5 thousand kilometers) of the intra-farm irrigation network needs reconstruction, 17.4 percent needs repair;
- 18 of the 42 water intake hydroelectric units with a capacity of 10 m³ to 300 m³ per second require replacement and modernization of hydromechanical equipment, and 5 hydroelectric units require reconstruction;
- most of the pumping stations serving nearly 2.1 million hectares of land have exhausted their resources, 76 out of 1130 stations are rare (>100 m³/s), 496 are average (up to 10 m³/s) and 561 are small (less than 1 m³/s) pumping stations. 80% of large pumping stations, 50% of medium stations and 30% of small stations need repair and reconstruction;
- a sharp increase in the price of energy sources and an increase in the cost of equipment has changed it in favor of runoff irrigation;
- 11 out of 27 inspected water reservoirs are almost filled with mud, and in 5, the volume of sediments is close to the height of the water discharge structures;
- about 19,000 kilometers of open drains in domestic farms require cleaning, 11,500 kilometers of open and closed drains need reconstruction and repair, no more than 50% of closed horizontal drains are working.

In such a situation, the technical resources of the infrastructure may decrease further and lead to a complicated situation.

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